

STRENGTHENING PREVENTIVE MEASURES AMONG YOUTH IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In this article, work with juvenile delinquents, prevention of crime among them, assistance in the adaptation of juveniles who have served their sentence to social life, prevention of their involvement in various currents, and coordination of the efforts of the bodies responsible for this area and the work of these bodies normative and legal documents serving to fully ensure its effectiveness are analytically described.

Key words: Uzbekistan, United Nations, minors, rights and freedoms, legal framework.

In Uzbekistan, the issue of ensuring the rights and freedoms of minors, protecting their legal interests, and most importantly, raising a mature generation, has risen to the level of state policy. The creation of a solid legal framework for the protection of the interests of minors is an important factor in the introduction of an effective social protection system and material and moral support for young people. Currently, 40 percent of the population of our country are minors. This indicator alone shows how urgent the issue is. In this process, parents, neighborhood, educational institutions and the general public have a huge responsibility. In particular, less than 3 months after gaining independence, on November 20, 1991, the Law "On the Basics of Youth Policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. By 2016, the new version of the law "On State Policy Regarding Youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. In addition, the laws "On the guarantees of children's rights", "On the prevention of lack of control and offenses among minors", "On the protection of children from information harmful to their health" were adopted, and a number of international documents were ratified.

According to statistical data, crime committed by minors in 1996 compared to 1995 was 9.5% in the republic, or 18.9% in Samarkand region, with a decrease from 3243 to 3558¹.

In 1996, 3,243 crimes were committed by minors in the republic, and in 1997, the total number of crimes was 3,189, which is 1.7%, while the number of minors participating in the crime decreased from 3,045 to 3,025, or 0.7%².

¹ NA Uz, M-76-fund, 1-list, 1505-case, 1-sheet

However, the crime committed by minors increased by 3% in Syrdaryodarya region, 17.6% in Tashkent region, 25.6% in Namangan region, and 42.4% in Jizzakh, which led to a serious shortage of law enforcement officers³.

In the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, due to the failure of the employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs to identify teenagers who do not study and work, and to include them in the preventive system, crimes committed by minors in the 6th month of 2002 were 1.7% more than last year in the republic, in particular, 41% increase in Khorezm region, 14% increase in Tashkent city, 12% increase in Ferganada region.

In 2002, homicides by or involving minors decreased by 23.5% nationwide, while grievous bodily harm increased by 53.3%, assault by 32%, robbery by 7.5%, and hooliganism by 8.7%⁴.

In 2002, the number of drug-related crimes committed by minors was 56.5% (10-23), while this indicator decreased in all regions, in Samarkand region, the commission of this type of crime increased by 33.3% (4-3).

Law No. ORQ-263 of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 29, 2010 "On prevention of delinquency and delinquency among minors" defines the legal basis for prevention of delinquency and delinquency among minors in Uzbekistan.⁵

In connection with the liberalization of criminal legislation in our country, as a result of paying special attention to solving the issue of responsibility of minors based on humane and fair principles, the total number of crimes committed in the republic in 2017 compared to 2013 decreased by 18.3%, of which: the share of minors decreased by 30.2% decreased. Persons who committed crimes decreased by 17.0%, minors decreased by 35%. School students decreased by 10%, college and high school students by 24.5%. However, crimes committed by schoolchildren increased by 4.0% in 2017 compared to 2016. Also, the share of minors in the total number of criminals has not decreased, this figure was 2.2% in 2016 and 2.2% in 2017. In addition, crimes committed by schoolchildren decreased by only 10% from 2013 to 2017⁶.

² NA Uz, M-76-fund, 1-list, 1001- case, 142-sheet

³ NA Uz, M-76-fund, 1-list, 1001- case, 142-sheet

⁴ NA Uz, M-76-fund, 1-list, 1874- case, 9-sheet

⁵ <https://lex.uz/docs/1685726?twolang=1>

⁶ Gofurov Sh.R. Voyaga yetmaganlar o'rtasida huquqbuzarliklar profilaktikasini takomillashtirish masalalari // O'zbekiston Respublikasi Hukumatining Akademiya'sining axborotnomasi. – 2017. – №50 – B.64.

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The highest level of juvenile criminal activity in the last five years is observed in Tashkent region, Tashkent city, Fergana, Andijan, Samarkand, Namangan, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions, the lowest indicators are observed in Jizzakh, Khorezm, Navoi, Syrdarya, Bukhara regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Crimes committed by minors amounted to 2.8% in 2013, 2.7% in 2014, 2.4% in 2015, 2.2% in 2016, 2.1% in 2017, and over the past five years by minors committed crimes decreased by 31.5 percent.

Based on the decision, analysis shows that during 2018, a total of 1276 minors committed various types of crimes. A total of 739 crimes were committed by minors in 2019. 49% of minor offenders are students of secondary special educational institutions and 25% are schoolchildren⁷.

As a result of the actions taken, as of July 2019, youth crime was observed 4,549 times, which is a 39.1% decrease compared to last year. Also, 78.9% in Tashkent city, 67.3% in Andijan region, 51.9% in Samarkand region, 46.5% in Jizzakh region, 44.4% in Namangan region, 39% in Syrdarya region, 38.7% in Khorezm region, Navoi region 33.7 percent, 33.3 percent in Fergana region, 25.7 percent in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 20.8 percent in Tashkent region, 14.5 percent in Bukhara region, 9.4 percent in Kashkadarya region, and 3.1 percent in Surkhandarya region.

Juvenile crime has decreased by 32.9% compared to the previous period, in terms of regions: 76.9% in Khorezm region, 75% in Navoi region, 62.7% in Namangan region, 56% in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 46.9% in Bukhara region, 46% in Samarkand region, 37 percent, 38.5 percent in Tashkent city, 36.6 percent in Andijan region, 33 percent in Syrdarya region, 11.8 percent in Kashkadarya region, 10 percent in Surkhandarya region, 8 percent in Jizzakh region, and 5.1 percent in Fergana region. increased by 4.1% in Tashkent region due to insufficient organization of cooperation with relevant organizations, ineffectiveness of work in curbing juvenile crime⁸.

So, in recent years, a lot of work has been done in the implementation of preventive measures among young people, and many measures are taken to reduce crime among them.

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⁸<https://xs.uz/uzkr/post/yoshlar-zhinojatchiligi-39-1-foizga-kamajdi-qandaj-711b>

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